

Edge-Based Eulerian Quantum Walks: Spectral and Topological Properties for Quantum Transport

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Abstract—Quantum walks are central to quantum computation, simulation, and transport, but extending discrete-time walks to directed graphs is challenging because unitary evolution must preserve probability while respecting edge orientation. We study directed Eulerian graphs, where balanced in- and out-degree allows incoming directed-edge amplitudes to scatter unitarily into outgoing ones. Using an edge-based Hilbert space and local Grover scattering, we construct a global unitary walk operator and compare its dynamics with random local-unitary baselines on the same topology. The Eulerian Grover walk exhibits stronger recurrence, higher localization, and more structured spectral behaviour, indicating that directed Eulerian structure can shape coherent quantum transport.

Index Terms—Quantum algorithms, directed graphs, quantum information science, spectral analysis, network topology, quantum transport.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum walks provide a unitary framework for studying transport, interference, localization, and recurrence on graph-structured systems. While standard constructions are often formulated on undirected graphs, directed graphs introduce an additional constraint: unitary evolution must preserve probability while respecting edge orientation. This requires local updates that map incoming degrees of freedom to outgoing degrees of freedom with matching dimension.

Directed Eulerian graphs satisfy this requirement naturally, since every vertex has equal in-degree and out-degree. In this work, we study an edge-based discrete-time quantum walk in which basis states correspond to directed edges and local Grover-type scattering maps incoming edge amplitudes to outgoing ones. We compare the resulting Eulerian Grover walk with a random local-unitary baseline on the same topology, using return probability, inverse participation ratio, eigenphase structure, eigenmode localization, and preliminary winding/interface diagnostics to connect directed graph structure with quantum transport behaviour.

II. MODEL

We study a discrete-time quantum walk on a finite directed Eulerian graph $G = (V, E)$ satisfying

$$\deg^+(v) = \deg^-(v) = d_v \quad (1)$$

at every vertex. The Eulerian condition ensures that the number of incoming and outgoing directed-edge states match locally, allowing each vertex update to be represented by a square unitary scattering matrix. We define the Hilbert space on directed edges,

$$\mathcal{H} = \text{span}\{|e\rangle : e \in E\}. \quad (2)$$

At each vertex v , incoming edge amplitudes are scattered to outgoing edge amplitudes using the Grover coin

$$C_v = \frac{2}{d_v}J - I, \quad (3)$$

where J is the all-ones matrix and I is the identity. Assembling these local scattering maps over all vertices gives a global walk operator U_E with evolution [1]

$$|\psi(t+1)\rangle = U_E|\psi(t)\rangle. \quad (4)$$

We verify unitarity numerically through $U_E^\dagger U_E = I$.

We initialize the walk on a single directed edge state $|e_0\rangle$ and quantify the dynamics using return probability, long-time edge occupation, and inverse participation ratio [2]–[4]. As a baseline, we replace each Grover coin with a random local unitary $R_v \in U(d_v)$, generated by QR decomposition, producing a comparison operator U_R on the same graph and initial state.

To connect dynamics with spectral structure, we compute eigenvalues and eigenvectors [5], [6]

$$U\phi_k = \lambda_k\phi_k, \quad \lambda_k = e^{i\theta_k}, \quad (5)$$

and measure eigenmode localization using eigenvector IPR. We also consider a minimal periodic directed-edge model with two channels per unit cell,

$$U(k) = S(k)C(\theta), \quad (6)$$

to examine quasienergy bands and interface-localized behaviour in translation-invariant Eulerian walks [7], [8].

Fig. 1. Comparison of Eulerian Grover and random local-unitary walks on the same directed Eulerian topology. The Grover walk shows stronger return-probability revivals, higher dynamical localization as measured by IPR, and more localized eigenmodes in the spectral IPR comparison.

III. RESULTS

We compare the Eulerian Grover quantum walk against a random local-unitary walk defined on the same directed Eulerian topology. Both walks are unitary and evolve on the directed-edge Hilbert space, so differences in behaviour arise from the local scattering rule rather than from the underlying graph structure.

Figure 1 shows that the Eulerian Grover walk exhibits stronger recurrence and localization than the random local-unitary baseline. Starting from the same localized edge state, the Grover walk produces pronounced return-probability revivals at later times, indicating coherent refocusing of amplitude near the initial edge. The inverse participation ratio shows the same trend. It remains higher for the Grover walk over much of the evolution, especially at early and intermediate times. Since higher IPR corresponds to probability being concentrated on fewer directed-edge states, this suggests that Grover scattering preserves graph-dependent interference pathways rather than spreading uniformly. By contrast, the random local-unitary walk shows weaker recurrence and broader edge-state occupation.

The spectral localization comparison in Figure 1 provides a mechanism for the observed recurrence and localization. Both the Eulerian Grover and random local-unitary operators have eigenvalues on the unit circle, as expected for unitary evolution, but their spectral structure differs. The Grover walk

shows more organized eigenphase spacing, including repeated or nearly repeated phases, while the random baseline has a less structured phase distribution. The Grover operator also contains higher-IPR eigenmodes, indicating that several eigenvectors are concentrated on smaller directed substructures of the graph. When the localized initial state overlaps with these modes, amplitude can remain partially trapped or coherently return, explaining the stronger return-probability revivals and elevated dynamical IPR observed in the Grover walk.

As a first step toward topological Eulerian quantum walks, we studied a translation-invariant one-dimensional Eulerian walk with two directed edge channels per unit cell. This allows the walk to be written as a momentum-space Floquet operator $U(k) = S(k)C(\theta)$ [1], whose eigenphases define quasienergy bands. We then introduced a finite interface between two regions with different coin parameters. For opposite-sign coin angles, the finite-chain spectrum contains modes sharply localized near the interface, with eigenphases near $\pm\pi/2$. These preliminary interface-localized states suggest that Eulerian-constrained quantum walks may support boundary or defect modes associated with structured Floquet spectra.

IV. CONCLUSION

We developed an edge-based discrete-time quantum walk framework for directed Eulerian graphs, using local Grover scattering to construct a global unitary evolution on directed-edge states. Compared with random local-unitary walks on the same topology, the Eulerian Grover walk shows stronger recurrence, higher localization, and more structured eigenphase and eigenmode behaviour. Preliminary periodic and interface models suggest that these spectral features may extend toward boundary-localized transport in directed systems. Testing the stability of recurrence, circulation, and interface modes under defects, perturbations, and disorder will clarify whether Eulerian quantum walks can support robust quantum transport.

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